

Optimization and kinetic modelling of biodiesel produced from *Ficus carica* seed oil (a novel feedstock) using response surface methodology

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ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLE

ABSTRACT

The seed oil of *Ficus carica* was subjected to transesterification reaction using KOH as catalyst and excess methanol to produce fatty acid methyl ester (biodiesel). The physicochemical properties of the fig seed oil and biodiesel was characterized using standard analytical methods. Similarly, the lipid composition was evaluated using gas chromatography coupled with flame ionization detector technique. The various functional groups present in the biodiesel were investigated using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The results of the lipid analysis revealed that polyunsaturated fatty acids were the predominant fatty acid in the seed oil, while the FTIR analysis on the biodiesel, revealed the presence of O-H, C-H, C-O, C-C groups. The effects of process parameters such as temperature, catalyst concentration, reaction time and methanol/oil ratio were investigated using batch mode. The significance of these process parameters as well as their effects on the transesterification proficiency were established using full factorial central composite design and were optimized with the response surface (RSM) methodology. From the analysis, the feedstock gave an optimum yield of 90% when the temperature was at 60 °C for 50 min with 0.6 g of KOH catalyst and 6:1 methanol/oil ratio. The results of the physicochemical properties were compared with ASTM D6751 standards and the parameter values were in agreement with the standard. Thus, the study proved that fig seed oil is an efficient feedstock for biodiesel production.

KEYWORDS

biodiesel; central composite design; *Ficus carica* seed oil; optimization; transesterification

1. INTRODUCTION

The combustion of fossil fuels is usually characterized with the emission of greenhouse gases such as nitrous oxides, carbon (IV) oxides, methane, which are sources of environmental pollution and are major contributors to global warming. These increasing rates of environmental pollution combined with a current short supply of fossil fuels, has resulted in search for alternative sources of energy. Biodiesel is an alternative form of fuel which is similar to the conventional fossil diesel. However, this form of fuel is highly eco-

friendly owing to its non-emission of CO₂. Majority of the world's energy consumption and the energy needed in the transportation sector is met by fossil fuels (Dorian et al., 2006). The production of biodiesel from edible and non-edible plant oils and animals is possible through a base catalysed trans-esterification with alcohol which extracts glycerine as a by-product from the oil. In its purest form, it can be used as fuels for vehicles, but it is usually used as a diesel additive to reduce levels of CO emissions from diesel-powered vehicle. Biodiesel is a renewable energy source and due to its eco-friendly nature, its use has become widely acceptable all over the world of late (Saucedo, 2001).

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Moreover, they have practically no sulphur content, offer no storage difficulty, and possess good lubrication properties. Du et al. (2004) reported that there is almost a zero emission of CO₂ in vehicle engines that uses biodiesel. When compared with petro-diesel, it reduces about half of the emission of particulate matter, unburned hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide, most part of the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and sulphates. Studies have shown that the rate of emission of nitrogen oxides is very minimal with biodiesel compared to petro-diesel (Tickell, 1999). Different biodiesel blends can be obtained by mixing it with petroleum-based diesel in any proportion and can be used in most compression-ignition engines with little or no modifications (Khan and Chhetri, 2000). Biodiesel is shown to be produced from vegetable oils such as Palm oil (Kheang et al., 2011), orange oil (Purushothaman and Nagarajan, 2009), cotton seed oil (Nabi et al., 2009), soybean oil (Can et al., 2016), olive oil (Lo, 2003), nerium oil (Pradeep, 2013), frying palm oil (Ozsezen et al., 2008), peanut (Faircloth et al., 2008), jatropha and karnja (Longman, 2016), *Calophyllum inophyllum* oil (Rahman et al., 2013), waste lemon peels (Giovanna et al., 2014), sun flower oil (Rakopoulos et al., 2008) and mustard oil (Krishna et al., 2016). Over 90% of commercial biodiesel is produced from edible plant oils (Shikha and Rita, 2012). Researchers have advocated for the production of biodiesel using non-edible plant oils which are deemed cost-effective as the plants can be cultivated on waste lands that are even less fertile and can grow comfortably with minimal care (Fatah et al., 2012; Atabani and Ong, 2013). One of the major arguments in the production of biodiesel from edible plant oil is that it might likely cause shortage of edible oil for human consumption as such production from non-edible feedstocks are encouraged (Chhetri et al., 2008; Mahanta et al., 2006). Non-edible plant oil contains toxic compounds and as such unfit for human consumption which makes them suitable feedstocks. (Bankovic-Ilic et al., 2012). Non-edible plant oils are preferred for use in biodiesel production owing to its biodegradable nature, low sulphur content and high combustion efficiency (Shikha and Rita, 2012). *Ficus carica* also known as fig belongs to themoraceae family (Badgujar et al., 2014). With over 700 species, it is commonly found in the Mediterranean and Southwest Asia region (Badgujar et al., 2014). Vinson et al. (2005) reported that fig contains some phytochemicals such as polyphenols and proanthocyanidins. In this study, *Ficus carica* seed oil was investigated as a potential feedstock for biodiesel production.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Sample collection

The fruits were collected from Lewe community in Gokana local government area of Rivers State. All the reagents for the experiment were procured at Reigneth stores Intl Ltd., Mushin, Lagos and were of analytical grade.

2.2. Sample preparation

The seeds of the *Ficus carica* were separated from the fruit pod. The seeds and fruit pods were dried at room temperature for 4 weeks and blended separately into powder using a heavy duty miller (grinder).

2.3. Oil extraction and determination of oil content

Seeds from each crushed sample (500 g) were fed to a soxhlet extractor fitted with a 2 L round bottomed flask (Paquot, 1979). The extraction was executed on a water bath for 6 h with n-hexane. The solvent was removed under vacuum, using a rotary evaporator. The amount of oil extracted was determined using the following equation,

$$\text{Oil content (\%)} = (\text{weight of oil extracted}) / (\text{weight of seed}) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.4. Production of biodiesel from feedstock

One liter of the extracted crude oil was measured out and poured into 2 L round bottom flask equipped with reflux condenser, magnetic stirrer and thermometer. The oil was then pre-heated to 100 °C in order to remove excess moisture using a water bath. About 0.70% (w/w) NaOH was dissolved in a 6:1 molar ratio of n-hexane/oil and was dissolved completely until sodium methoxide was formed. The resulting sodium methoxide solution was then added to the pre-heated oil in a 250 mL three-neck glass flask and placed on a hot plate magnetic stirrer at a speed of 400 rpm. The reaction was timed for 60 min. The mixture was cooled at room temperature of the reaction was kept overnight for the separation of the two distinct layers. Two layers were observed; a thick brown layer (glycerol) at the bottom and a yellowish colour layer constituting the biodiesel (Fatty acid methyl ester) was seen in the upper layer. The

crude biodiesel in the upper layer was then purified by distilling the residual methanol at 60°C. The remaining catalyst was then removed by successive rinsing with 50ml of distilled water. About 1-2 drops of acetic acid was added to neutralize the catalyst. The residual was then eliminated by treating with anhydrous Na₂SO₄ followed by filtration. A transparent blackish liquid is obtained as the final product. The crude biodiesel undergoes refining in a degumming process to remove gums, phosphatides and other complex compounds capable of causing hydrolysis and interfering in the transesterification process. This was done by heating the oil to a temperature of 80°C with constant whirling at 1000 rpm in a glass vessel with thermostat. About 0.2% of phosphoric acid and 3% distilled water was added to the pre-heated oil. The mixture was stir for 1 h and the white precipitate formed was separated by centrifugation for 0.5 h at 3500 rpm and the degummed oil was dried at 100°C for 20 min. Then, 0.5 M NaOH solution was added to the degummed oil and whirled in a glass vessel to neutralize the free fatty acids. NaCl (about 10% of the weight of the oil) was added to help settle out the soap formed. The mixture was transferred into a separating funnel and allowed to stand for one hour the soap formed was separated from the oil. Hot water was added to the oil solution until the soap remaining in the solution was eliminated. The neutralized oil was then drawn off into a beaker. This reaction was carried out at varying temperatures, methanol ratio, quantity of catalysts, and reaction time according to the experimental design matrix. This was to ascertain their effects on the percentage yield of the biodiesel (FAME). Percentage yield was calculated using following equation,

$$\% \text{ Yield} = (\text{weight of fatty acid methy ester}) / (\text{weight of oil used}) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

2.5. Physicochemical analysis

2.5.1. Determination of moisture content

2 g of the crude oil and biodiesel each were weighed out and was dried in an oven set at 105°C for 3 h. The weights of the samples were measured every 10 min until a change of not more than 0.001 g was observed. The results of each dry sample was determined and recorded. The percentage moisture content was calculated using following equation,

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = (\text{wet weight-dry weight}) / (\text{wet weight}) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

2.5.2. Determination of iodine value

Iodine value was determined by IUPAC procedure using Wijs method. (Paquot, 1979). 0.4 g each of oil and biodiesel was weighed into an iodine flask and was dissolved in a 15 mL CCl₄ solution. 25 mL of Wijs reagent was mixed with the solution and the flask was stoppered and shaken gently. It was placed in the dark for 30 min. 20 mL of potassium iodide solution and 150 mL of water was added. It was titrated with 0.002 M sodium thiosulphate solution using starch solution as indicator; the titration was continued until the blue colour just disappears after vigorous shaking. A blank test was also carried simultaneously without the samples.

Iodine value was calculated using following equation,

$$I.V = (12.69 \times N \times (V_B - V_A)) / m \quad (4)$$

where N is standard normality of sodium thiosulphate, V_B is titre value for blank, V_A is titre value for sample and m is the mass of the sample.

2.5.3. Determination of peroxide value

2.0 g each of oil and biodiesel were weighed out into a 125 mL Erlenmeyer flask. 30 mL each of acetic acid and chloroform in the ratio of 3:2 was added to the samples and swirled for 1 min. 0.5 mL of saturated KI solution was added using pipette and swirled for 1 min (light brown colour is observed). Another 30 mL of distilled water was added and then titrated with 0.01 M sodium thiosulphate until the solution becomes pale yellow. 1 mL starch indicator solution was added and titration continued until the blue colour disappears. A blank test was also carried simultaneously without the samples

Peroxide value (P.V) calculated using following equation,

$$P.V = (S \times M) / (\text{sample weight}) \times 1000 \quad (5)$$

Where S is the volume (mL) of sodium thiosulphate used in the titration after correction for the blank titration and M is the molar concentration of sodium thiosulphate.

2.5.4. Determination of saponification number.

The saponification value (S.V) was determined by IUPAC method (Paquot, 1979). 2 g each of oil and biodiesel were weighed accurately into a round bottom flask. 25 mL of ethanolic KOH solution was added to the samples and boiled. After 60 min of heating, 0.5 mL of phenolphthalein was added and titrated with

hydrochloric acid solution until the colour of indicator changes. A blank test was also carried simultaneously without the samples. Saponification value was calculated using following equation,

$$S.V = (56.1 \times N \times (V_B - V_A)) / m \quad (6)$$

where N is the standard normality of hydrochloric acid solution, V_B is titre value for blank, V_A is titre value for sample and m is mass of sample.

2.5.5. Determination of acid value

1 g of each of oil and biodiesel was dissolved in a 25 mL equal volume of diethyl ether and absolute ethanol. The solution was then titrated with 0.1 M potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution, using 0.3 mL phenolphthalein as an indicator. The titration was continued, until a pink colour solution was obtained. The acid value (A.V) was calculated using following equation,

$$A.V = (56.1 \times N \times V) / m \quad (7)$$

where V is the titre value (mL), N is standardized normality of KOH solution; and m is the mass of the samples.

2.5.6. Determination of free fatty acid (FFA)

Free fatty acid content is determined as per IUPAC standard which is described as follows (Paquot, 1979). 1 g each oil and biodiesel was weighed into a conical flask and was dissolve in a 25 ml equal volume of diethyl ether and absolute ethanol solvent. 0.3mL of phenolphthalein served as the indicator and was titrated with the solution of KOH. The titration was continued until a pink colour solution was obtained indicating the end point of the reaction. The FFA concentration was calculated as percentage oleic acid from a titration value as presented in following equation,

$$FFA (\%) = ((V-b) \times N \times 28.2) / m \quad (8)$$

where V, b, N and m are the volume (mL) of titration solution, volume (mL) of the blank (initial), normality of the titration solution and mass of the samples (g) respectively.

2.5.7. Determination of ester value

The ester value of the oil and biodiesel samples was calculated as the difference between the saponification value and the acid value as presented in following equation,

$$\text{Ester value} = S.V - A.V \quad (9)$$

2.5.8. Determination of specific gravity

An empty 25 mL specific gravity bottle was weighed. The bottle was filled with water and reweighed. After, draining the water in the bottle, oil and biodiesel sample each was poured into the bottles and the weights were taken. The experiment was done at room temperature the specific gravity was calculated using following equation,

$$\text{Specific gravity} = (\text{Weight of sample}) / (\text{weight of equal volume of water}) \quad (10)$$

2.5.9. Determination of refractive index

A few drops of oil and biodiesel sample were placed on the glass slide of the refractometer. Water at 30° C was circulated round the glass slide in other to obtain a uniform temperature. A fluorescence tube was brought closer to the apparatus at the glass slide and monitored through the aperture. The centre of the circle was adjusted (taken down) to where it corresponds to the graduated scale pointed to the refractive index. Hence the refractive indexes of the oil and biodiesel were determined.

2.5.10. Determination of kinematic viscosity

The method of Brookfield as described in ASTM D2983. A rotary viscometer was used. The samples (oil and biodiesel) was placed in a glass tube and housed in an insulated block at a fixed temperature. The metal spindle was then rotated with samples at a fixed rpm, based on the internal resistance to rotation by the shear stress of the oil's absolute viscosity can be determined. The results were obtained and recorded in mm²/s.

2.5.11. Determination of boiling point

30 mL each of biodiesel and oil was poured into a heating beaker and thermometer inserted. The beaker with the samples was heated separately with a hot plate. As the temperature increases, the point at which the samples started boiling was noted and recorded.

2.5.12. Determination of cloud and pour points

A cooling bath containing a freezing mixture of salt and water to obtain a lower range of temperature was used. 50 mL of the fatty acid methyl ester and oil were placed in a glass jar and the temperature was lowered until clouds of crystals appeared at the bottom of the jar. 20 mL sample each of biodiesel and oil was poured into a beaker, corked and kept in a refrigerator to solidify. When the sample was brought out and kept in the open,

the temperature at which it melts and starts flowing was noted and recorded. variable.

2.5.13. Lipid composition analysis

The various fatty acids in the *Ficus carica* seed oil was quantified using gas chromatography coupled to flame iodination detector. GC/FID (Agilent 7820A). Split less mode injection method was deployed and DB-5ms capillary chromatographic columns of 30 m × 0.25 mm (inner diameter) × 0.25 μm (film thickness) was used. The injection port temperature was maintained at 260 °C, while the column temperature was initially set at 100 °C for 3 min, and was later increased to 270 °C at 10 °C/min interval, and kept for 2 min; it was finally increased to 300 °C at 10 °C/min intervals and maintained for 15 min. The detector temperature was 280 °C. The carrier gas was hydrogen while the make-up gas was air with flow rate of 10 mL/min. Fatty acid compositions present in the seed oils were identified viz a viz the appropriate retention time window for each compound in the calibration solutions with the help of GC/FID peak identification software.

2.6 Instrumental characterization

Fourier Transfer Infrared analysis the biodiesel was characterized using FTIR 8400S spectrophotometer for the determination of functional groups present in biodiesel.

2.7 Design of Experiment

Central Composite Design (CCD) is the experimental design selected for this study and the response measured is the dependent variable which is the yield of biodiesel. The optimized process variables for biodiesel production from the seed of *Ficus carica* oil via transesterification are reaction temperature, catalyst amount, reaction time and methanol ratio on yield of biodiesel. Model of seven-levels, four factors Central Composite Design (CCD) which include $2^4 = 16$ factorial points plus 6 central points and $2 \times 4 = 8$ star points leading to total of 30 experimental runs was adopted in this study. Table 1 showed the independent factors and their corresponding actual values of the designated process parameters. Table 2 showed the coded values of the experimental runs. The coded values for the 4 process variables were varied at seven levels (-α, -2, -1, 0, +1, +2, +α). The factor levels of the variables investigated were selected by studying the effect of individual variables on biodiesel yield and operating limits of the biodiesel production process

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the physicochemical properties of the *Ficus carica* seed oil as compared with ASTM D6751 were presented in Table 3. From the result, it was observed that the kinematic viscosity, specific gravity, moisture content, flash point, were in the ranges of the standard of ASTM D6751. Acid value, peroxide value, kinematic viscosity, iodine value, saponification values are associated with the oxidative features of the fuel. After the transesterification process, the iodine value was seen to have decreased from 74.6 to 72.8. Iodine number is a measure of the degree of unsaturation; it is a crucial parameter when evaluating the oxidative stability of biodiesel and vegetable oils (Samara and Fabio, 2018). A high iodine value indicates the presence of increased amount of unsaturated fatty acids present in the biodiesel. Higher degree of unsaturation may result in the polymerization of the lubricating engine oil and subsequently its deterioration (Environment Australia, 2003). The iodine value of biodiesel produced from the seed oil of *Ficus carica* oil decreased when compared with ASTM D6751 standard which indicates that it has a tendency to undergo slow oxidative process and thereby represents better quality oil. Similarly, the saponification values were also seen to have decreased from 235.5-188.9. An increase in the saponification values of a biodiesel indicates increase fatty acids with time due to oxidation reactions. The peroxide value was increased after the transesterification; this could lead to the high rate of peroxide formation. Peroxide values are used to monitor oxidative progression and the formation of secondary oxidation products. (Dunn, 2002) . One of the major problems of biodiesel is the oxidation instability. Unsaturated fatty acids are more likely to undergo oxidation than saturated fatty acids. This is mainly due to the presence of unstable double bonds in the unsaturated fatty acid chains which offers a high level of affinity towards reaction with oxygen especially if exposed to air or water. (Su and White, 2004; Watkins et al., 2004). Oxidation of biodiesel can also be caused by poor storage conditions such as light, high temperature, contamination with metal. (Choe and Min, 2007; Dana, 2003; Natarajan, 2012). These factors are capable of initiating a couple of chemical reactions such as hydrolysis, photolysis, thermal polymerization, isomer cyclization and thermolytic reactions (Arora et al., 2009). Therefore it is important to prevent biodiesel from degradation. The kinematic viscosity of

Table 1. Process variables and levels used for response surface design of *Ficus carica* oil transesterification

Independent variables	Units	Symbols	Levels						
			- α	-2	-1	0	+1	+2	+ α
Time	Mins	A	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
Temperature	°C	B	20	30	40	50	60	70	80
Catalyst	Wt%	C	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Methanol ratio	-	D	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

Table 2. Experimental design matrix of *Ficus carica* oil transesterification

Run	Coded factors				Yield (%)
	A	B	C	D	
1	-2	+ α	-1	- α	68.23
2	0	0	- α	-1	76.17
3	-1	-2	0	0	71.31
4	+2	0	+1	+2	59.22
5	- α	+2	+ α	+1	61.9
6	+1	- α	+2	+ α	82.15
7	- α	+1	-2	-2	76.34
8	-1	- α	+ α	+1	66.25
9	+1	0	+2	+2	72.42
10	0	+1	-1	+ α	78.36
11	-2	+ α	-2	- α	68.39
12	+ α	+1	0	-2	81.09
13	+2	+ α	- α	0	90.32
14	+ α	+2	0	-2	85.3
15	- α	-1	+ α	-1	81.37
16	-2	+1	-2	+1	63.08
17	0	- α	- α	+1	85.89
18	+1	-1	0	0	85.34
19	-1	-2	+2	+2	71.31
20	+2	0	+ α	+ α	81.23
21	+1	+1	-1	-2	80.34
22	- α	+ α	- α	+2	75.3
23	0	+2	+ α	+ α	76.29
24	+2	+2	-1	+ α	81.36
25	-1	-2	+1	- α	68.29
26	0	-1	0	-1	85.47
27	+1	0	-2	0	78.32
28	+ α	- α	+2	+2	86.38
29	- α	+2	+2	+1	88.38
30	0	-2	+ α	- α	86.36

the biodiesel was in agreement with the ASTM D6751 range of (1.9-6.0). The kinematic viscosity decreased from 6.0 to 3.80 after transesterification. Biodiesel with high viscosity are unsuitable for direct usage as engine fuels because it results in carbon deposits, oil ring sticking, thickening and gelling of lubricating oil. Biodiesel with low viscosity values results in high flow rate and as such a good quality biodiesel. The moisture content was seen to increase when compared with the ASTM standard. Biodiesels absorb more moisture and has water retaining capacity than hydrocarbon diesel. This is usually not good as it leads to water accumulation and growth of microbes in the fuel handling, storage and transportation equipment.

The results of the lipid composition analysis of the fig seeds oil revealed that the predominant fatty acid present in the seed oil are oleic acid, linoleic acid, Palmitic acids with percentage compositions of 33.17%, 15.82% and 5.99% respectively. The analysis further revealed that polysaturated fatty acids were the most predominant (33.67±0.76) followed by monounsaturated fatty acid and saturated fatty acids with values 16.09±0.094 and 9.17±0.598 respectively. Morton, 1987 similarly reported that the major fatty acids of fig seed oil were palmitic, oleic, linoleic and γ-linoleic acids. Palmitic, arachidic and heneicosanoic acid were detected in smaller amounts compared to other fatty acids. Nazan et al. (2019) reported that

Palmitic acid, oleic acid and linoleic acid had the highest percentage in the fig seed oil analysis. From the analysis, it was observed that fig seed oil has more unsaturated fatty acids than saturated fatty acids. The implication is that the biodiesel will tend to emit more oxides of nitrogen and exhibit lower thermal efficiency when compared with biodiesel with saturated acids. Biodiesel with unsaturated fatty acids tend to have longer premixed combustion and higher peak pressure compared to biodiesel with high saturated fatty acids. Thus, this suggests that fig seed oil is an excellent source of biodiesel.

3.1. FTIR Characterization of biodiesel

The FTIR spectra of biodiesel produced from *Ficus carica* seed oil was carried out using spectroscopic technique. The detectable peaks were observed at 591.32 – 365.16 cm⁻¹ (O–H broad bend/alcohol), 720.10 cm⁻¹ (C–H weak rocking/alkanes), 873.52 cm⁻¹ (C–C strong bend/aromatics), 1174.15 - 1016.73 cm⁻¹ (C–C/C–O weak stretch/alcohol), 1364.72 cm⁻¹ (O–H weak double bending/alkynes), 1742.41 cm⁻¹ (C–O medium stretch/esters), 2354.37 cm⁻¹ (C–H weak finger print region/phenyl ring substitution), 2927.48 – 2859.37 cm⁻¹ (C–H weak stretch) and 3760.00 – 3472.29 cm⁻¹ (O–H strong stretch).

Table 3. Physicochemical properties of the *Ficus carica* seed oil

Properties	Units	crude oil from <i>Ficus carica</i>	Refined oil from <i>Ficus carica</i>	Biodiesel from <i>Ficus carica</i>	ASTM D6751
Moisture content	Wt.%	2.42	0.945	1.05	0.050 max
Kinematic Viscosity	mm ² /s	6.20	6.0	3.80	1.9-6.0
Acid value	MgKOH/g	11.90	4.7	2.5	0.50 max
Saponification value	MgKOH/g	275.8	235.5	188.9	-
Peroxide value	meqvO ₂ /kg	5.3	12.3	42.6	-
Iodine value	gI ₂ /100g	96.5	74.6	72.8	-
Specific gravity	g/cm ³	0.803	0.723	0.630	0.86-0.90
Free fatty acid	%	5.5	1.87	1.27	-
Flash point	°C	120	115	127	130 °C Min
Cloud point	°C	5	8	7	-
Refractive index	-	1.3243	1.2234	0.4564	-
Pour point	°C	6	4	3	-
Ester value		263.9	230.8	186.4	-
Physical state at room temp.		Liquid	Liquid	Liquid	-

Table 4. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the regression model equation, values of regression coefficients and their significant tests and effects.

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	P- value	Verdict
Model	2026.60	21	96.50	26.08	< 0.0001	Significant
B-temp	127.48	1	127.48	34.45	0.0004	
C-Catalyst	130.68	1	130.68	35.31	0.0003	
AB	161.22	1	161.22	43.57	0.0002	
AC	263.78	1	263.78	71.28	< 0.0001	
BC	41.78	1	41.78	11.29	0.0099	
BD	70.76	1	70.76	19.12	0.0024	
C ²	198.80	1	198.80	53.72	< 0.0001	
A ² D	196.66	1	196.66	53.15	< 0.0001	
B ² C	137.95	1	137.95	37.28	0.0003	
B ² D	457.34	1	457.34	123.59	< 0.0001	
BC ²	87.93	1	87.93	23.76	0.0012	
C ² D	266.08	1	266.08	71.90	< 0.0001	
A ² BD	278.01	1	278.01	75.13	< 0.0001	
A ² CD	19.93	1	19.93	5.39	0.0488	
A ² D ²	149.17	1	149.17	40.31	0.0002	
AB ³	45.28	1	45.28	12.24	0.0081	
AC ³	150.76	1	150.76	40.74	0.0002	
BC ³	27.65	1	27.65	7.47	0.0257	
A ² BC ³	24.71	1	24.71	6.68	0.0324	
A ² C ³ D	15.45	1	15.45	4.17	0.0753	
A ² CD ³	34.64	1	34.64	9.36	0.0156	
Residual	29.60	8	3.70			
Lack of fit	25.41	15	1.68	0.14	0.9959	not significant
Pure Error	35.92	3	12.23			
Cor Total	2056.21	29				

R² = 0.9856; R²_{adj} = 0.9478; R²_{pred} = 0.7938; Adeq Precision = 18.481

3.2. Model fitting

The response variables of the experimental matrix as shown in Table 4. The second order polynomial equation generated by Design-Expert 8 trial version software@2013 by Stat-Ease Inc., USA is presented in equation 1. However, to correlate the independent variables with response variables the linear, quadratic and the interaction of the process parameters is presented in following equation,

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^4 \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^4 \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=i+1}^4 \beta_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (11)$$

where Y is the response factor of FAME contents, X_i is the ith term of independent factor, β₀ is intercept, β_i is

the linear model coefficient, β_{ii} is quadratic coefficient for the factor i and β_{ij} is the linear model coefficient for the interaction between factors i and j.

The correlation between the experimental process variables and biodiesel yield produced from *Ficus caricas* was evaluated using the Central Composite Design (CCD) modeling techniques as shown in Table 4. The response yield of FAME (Y) and the process variable: Time (A), reaction temperature (B), catalyst amount (C) and methanol ratio (D) was fitted into the second order polynomial regression equation. The model for percentage of FAME content, Y in terms of the coded factors of the process variables in following equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Yield of FAME \%} = & +85.57 + 11.12B + 7.12C - 47.62AB \\ & -38.08AC - 17.41BC + 14.89BD - 12.86C^2 - 19.23 \\ & A^2D - 19.49 B^2C + 36.31 B^2D - 13.16BC^2 - 19.14C^2D \\ & -67.02A^2BD - 29.00 A^2CD - 34.00A^2D^2 + 32.45AB^3 \\ & + 29.54AC^3 + 16.41BC^3 - 23.99A^2BC^3 + 38.28A^2C^3D \\ & - 60.69A^2CD^3 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Table 4 showed that the linear terms of temperature, amount of catalyst, time, methanol oil molar ratio, quadratic terms of temperature, time, methanol oil molar ratio and interactive terms of time and temperature, time and catalyst, temperature and catalyst, temperature and methanol oil molar ratio, time and methanol oil molar ratio, catalyst and methanol oil molar ratio, time, temperature and methanol oil molar ratio, time, catalyst and methanol oil molar ratio that is AB, AC, BC, BD, A²D, C²D, A²BD, A²CD and A²BC³ are significant model terms. To obtain a statistically significant regression model, the significance of the regression coefficients was evaluated based on p-values. The coefficient terms with P-values more than 0.05 are insignificant and are removed from regression model. The model can reduce to equation 13 after eliminating the insignificant coefficients.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Yield of FAME (\%)} = & +85.57 + 11.12B + 7.12C - 47.62AB \\ & - 38.08AC - 17.41BC + 14.89BD - 12.86C^2 - 19.23A^2D - \\ & 19.49B^2C + 36.31B^2D - 13.16BC^2 - 19.14C^2D - 67.02A^2BD \\ & - 29.00A^2CD - 34.00A^2D^2 + 32.45AB^3 + 29.54AC^3 + \\ & 16.41BC^3 - 23.99A^2BC^3 - 60.69A^2CD^3 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The variance analysis gave a satisfactory yield of FAME depicting a significant quadratic and polynomial model with small P-value of 0.001 as presented in Table 4. High coefficient of determination, R² = 0.9856 proved that the model was significant and the adj R² value indicated that the selected model for the experimental design accurately predicted the experimental data with high variability of 98.56% and 94.78%. Table 4 showed a non-significant lack of fit value of 0.14 which is due to pure error and noise. Non-significant lack of fit is good because we want the model to fit. This is in agreement with the work done by (Dominic et al., 2017; Freedman et al., 1984). The Adeq precision (18.481) indicated that the signal was adequate since it is greater than 4. The plot of predicted and actual values of FAME yield as shown in Figure 1 indicated a good fit of experimental model (Hameed et al., 2009). The closer the points to the straight line, the closer the coefficient of determination (R²) to unity (R² = 0.9982) for the validation of experimental variables as shown

in Table 5. Deviation of plots from point of reference (perturbation curves) was also used to validate experimental variables as deviation from reference points indicated good correlation.

Table 5. Validation of process parameter used in transesterification reaction

Run order	Actual Value	Predicted Value
1	68.23	67.37
2	76.17	74.78
3	71.31	70.78
4	59.22	59.84
5	61.90	61.88

R² = 0.9982

3.3. Response surface plots of interaction of process variables

The interaction of the process variable on the % yield of FAME were observed by plotting 3-D surface curves against any two independent variables while other variables were kept at the centre (0) level. The 3-D curves of the response yield of methyl ester from the interactions between the variables are shown in Figure 2 – 6. The process variables were found to have significant interaction effects. The interactive effect of temperature and time on the yield of methyl ester is positive as shown in Figure 2. Increasing the temperature and time increased the yield of biodiesel this could be attributed to the fact that at higher reaction temperature there is higher rate of reaction as the reacting species collide more frequently at a more available time. Figure 3 showed the interaction of catalyst and time on the yield of biodiesel. The increase in the amount of catalyst and time, increased the yield of biodiesel, this could be due to increase in catalyst concentration which will increase the availability of catalysts for the reacting species thereby pushing the reaction forward in favor of increased yield of methyl ester. The response surface plot of the interactive effect of methanol oil mole ratio and time is shown in Figure 4. As the methanol oil mole ratio and time increased, the percentage yield of biodiesel declined. This could be attributed to the fact that the optimum molar ratio for maximum biodiesel yield was reached at 7 (Freedman et al., 1984). The interactive effect of methanol ratio and temperature is shown in Figure 5. It was observed that increase in methanol ratio and

Figure 1. Predicted versus actual value of FAME yield

Figure 2. Interaction effect of temperature and time on yield of biodiesel at constant catalyst amount and methanol molar ratio

Figure 3. Interaction effect of catalyst and time on yield of biodiesel at constant temperature

Figure 4. Interaction effect of methanol ratio and time on yield of biodiesel at constant catalyst amount and temperature

Figure 5. Interaction effect of methanol ratio and temperature on yield of biodiesel at constant catalyst amount and time

Figure 6. Interaction effect of methanol ratio and catalyst on yield of biodiesel at constant time and temperature

temperature, increased the yield of FAME. This could be at higher reaction temperature there is excitation of methanol that increased the yield of FAME. Reaction temperature and methanol to oil molar ratio are the most significant process variable that affect the yield of the FAME as indicated by their highest F values of 123.59 as shown in Table 4. Interactive effect of methanol ratio and catalyst on yield of biodiesel at constant time and temperature is shown in Figure 6. Increasing the methanol ratio and amount of catalyst increased the yield of FAME. This could be due to increase in catalyst concentration which will increase the availability of catalysts for the reacting species in the presence of optimum methanol oil.

The optimum values of the variables were: reaction temperature, 60 °C; time, 60 min; catalyst weight 0.6 and methanol molar ratio 6. The predicted response value at these optimum values was 95.57%. To confirm this optimum values, experiments were performed at these values and the experimental response value was 98.56%. This showed that the model correctly explained the influence of the process variables on the production of FAME from *Ficus carica* seed oil.

3.4. Kinetics of transesterification reaction

The overall transesterification reaction of *Ficus carica* oil with methanol is presented in following equation,

where FCT is the *Ficus carica* triglyceride, M is the methanol, F is the FAME and G is glycerin. The reaction was considered irreversible because excessive presence of methanol in the reaction. In this study, the overall reaction followed nth order was adopted to determine the best rate order using Pseudo first and Pseudo second model for the transesterification reaction is presented in following equation,

$$(-d[FCT])/dt = K[FCT]^n \quad (15)$$

Table 6. The values of k, E_a and R²

Order of reaction	K (min ⁻¹)	E _a (J/mol)	R ²
First order	2.49	34.92	0.924
Second order	45.12	297.43	0.199

3.4.1. Pseudo first order kinetics

The equation (16) shows an expression for Pseudo first order reaction.

$$\ln k = (-E_a/R)(1/T) + \ln k_0 \quad (16)$$

The plot of ln(k) against 1/T gives a slope of ((-E_a)/R), and intercept of ln(k).

where k₀ = Pre-exponential factor, E_a = activation energy, R = gas constant (8.314 J/mol), A = Absolute temperature.

3.4.2. Pseudo second order kinetics

Pseudo second order equation is shown in following equation,

$$1/((1-X_{FCT})) = k't \quad (17)$$

where k' = kC_{FCT}

The general rate constant and activation energy for Pseudo first order kinetics is presented in Table 6. The rate constant, k was calculated to be 2.49 min⁻¹ and activation energy, E_a is 34.92 mol⁻¹. Then, the rate equation for the pseudo first order kinetics model is shown in following equation,

$$-r_{FCT} = 2.49 C_{FCT0} [\exp(-4.2/T)](1-X_{FCT}) \quad (18)$$

The rate constant, k and activation energy, E_a is presented in Table 6. The rate constant, k is 45.12 min⁻¹ and E_a is 297.43 mol⁻¹. This is in agreement with Onukwuli et al., 2016; Kudiana and Sak, 2001; Komor, 2002. The rate equation for pseudo second order kinetics model is presented in following equation,

$$-r_{FCT} = 45.12 C_{FCT}^2 [\exp(-35.78/T)](1-X_{FCT})^2 \quad (19)$$

Table 6 showed the coefficient of determination, R² values, rate constants and activated energies. Pseudo first order reaction has the highest R² value of 0.929 which indicated that the reaction and process parameters fitted more into pseudo first order model.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, biodiesel was produced from fig seed oil through transesterification reaction which required alcohol in the presence of a catalyst. The kinetics of the transesterification was also investigated using five process parameters (temperature, methanol/oil ratio,

catalyst and time of reaction) and was optimized using surface response methodology. The feedstock gave an optimum yield of 90% when at 60 °C for 50 min with 0.6 g of KOH catalyst and 6:1 methanol/oil ratio. The under studied physicochemical parameters greatly aligns with the American system testing standards for biodiesel quality. Thus, the study lends support that fig seed oil can be a low-cost feedstock for an excellent biodiesel production. Further studies should be carried out to compare the total biodiesel yield of different nanocatalysts to the conventional catalysts.

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